

STRUCTURES DEVELOPMENT OF SMART UAV

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1. Introduction

The Smart UAV is designed to takeoff and land vertically, cruise like an airplane using tilting rotor mechanism which is located at wing tips. This paper presents a brief overview of development process of structures of smart UAV from initial conceptual design to final structural testing. Most of structures except joint fittings and some bulkheads made of composite materials to have weight and cost savings. The top design requirements of smart UAV are 5 hours flight times and 500 km/hr speed, 1000 kg takeoff weight with 40 kg payload. The structural design criteria are based on airworthiness requirements. The design approaches emphasize structural simplification, reduced part count, and easy handling. The composite coupon tests have been performed to establish lamina material properties, to confirm laminate design allowable stress, and to evaluate its structural strength. The heavy loaded critical parts such as wing-body joint and engine mounting support structures, and spar are tested to verify the design safety and stress analysis methods prior to built-in full-scale airframe. The design load conditions are about 220 cases for maneuvering, gust, and grounding. The stress analysis is based on finite element method using NASTRAN for full-scale airframe. Beside stress analysis, dynamic analysis to predict the vibration modes and frequencies and flutter speed also has been performed. The structures of smart UAV demonstrate the structural performance requirements under the expected critical load conditions as simulated by the full scale static test. Total test conditions are 11 critical cases of flight maneuvers and landing loads. The test article, which is one setup for 11 load conditions, is simulated to the flight and landing conditions using balancing system with actuators and restraint springs, and pulley. The test has been conducted to limit loads, ultimate loads

which are 1.5 times of limit loads, and failure load. Also the ground vibration test for flight prototype has been performed to confirm the vibration modes. The test results show that the structures of Smart UAV have been satisfied design strength and stiffness requirements. The final failure occurred at 165% load of critical load condition. The second flight airframe was revised by test results.

2. Design Procedures

The structures of Smart UAV were developed by the typical process shown in Fig. 1. The structural design requirements were identified based on the FAR 23 and 25, and other military specification.

Fig. 1. Structural design procedures

2.1 Design Loads

The flight envelope of Smart UAV is shown in Fig. 2. The load factors of helicopter and transition modes are 2g and of airplane mode is 3.5g. The design ultimate load is multiplied by 1.5 of safety factor. The 220 loading conditions based on FAR 23 and FAR 27 are defined, and the internal loads of those are calculated using ARGON of load analysis

tool which is KARI's internal program. Fig. 3 is one of internal load results which is described the critical wing bending moment diagram.

Fig. 2. V-n diagram

Fig. 3. Wing critical bending moment

2.2 Structural design

The configuration of smart UAV is shown in Fig. 4. The engine of smart UAV is located in the center fuselage. The engine shaft is connected to main center gear box to transmit the power into rotor gear boxes at wing tip.

The forward fuselage assembly is designed to hold mission payload, air data system and battery. The center fuselage assembly includes wing assembly with flaperon and nacelles. The center fuselage contains the main elements of propulsion system, avionics system, fuel tanks, landing gears system, center gear box of drive system, and flight control system. The keel beam structure of hat type configuration is designed to carry the main loads of landing and maneuverings.

The wing is composed of two spars, 12 ribs, lower and upper skins. The flaperon is one-piece sandwich panel attached to wing with three hinged joints. The

aft fuselage assembly has the vertical and horizontal stabilizers.

Fig. 4. Configuration of smart UAV

Most of parts are composite laminates and sandwich panel except for joint bulkheads as shown in Fig. 5. Specially, a carbon fiber reinforced BMI matrix using resin transfer moulding process is applied for high temperature zones around engine exhaust duct as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5. Structural layout for aluminum

Fig. 6. High Temperature RTM parts

The stress analysis is based on finite element method using NASTRAN. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show one of the stress results for hovering load case. The applied strains are below the design allowable strain of $4500 \mu S$. For members of margin of safety over 1.0 and below 0.0, the design iteration has been performed in order to optimize weight and strength.

Fig. 7. FEM results of full scale model

Fig. 8. Stress distributions of center spars

The structural parts of the smart UAV are below 250 pieces. The weight of the first prototype manufactured for static test was 181 kg. This means that the structural weight fraction is 0.18. Compared with other aluminum aircraft with 0.25 of structural weight fraction, it seems to be reduced weight as the results of using composite materials. The second manufactured airframe of flight prototype is 175 kg.

3. Test

The building block approach is applied for the composite structural testing. The coupon test for material properties, laminate element test for design allowables, components test for major loaded parts,

and full scale test have been performed.

As shown in Fig. 9, the coupon tests for tension, compression, shear, and joint have been performed.

(a) Tension test

(b) Compression test

(c) Shear test

(d) Joint Test

Fig. 9. Coupon tests

For components test, the rear spar which is most critical part of smart UAV was selected. As it is shown in Fig. 10, the rear spar has a big hole and curved flange for passage of the engine drive shaft. The test result of strains at critical point is shown in Fig. 11. Though strains are below the allowable, spar

occurred to fail at 155% load with upper flange buckled.

Fig. 10. Rear spar test

Fig. 11. Test result of rear spar

For full scale static test, eleven load cases which are the critical conditions for wing, fuselage and tail for maneuverings, gust, and landings are selected. The test loading system is one setup for time saving. The test article is floated as keeping 0 g state using the balancing system. As shown in Fig. 12, the restraints are imposed at dummy landings for safety. The loading type is yoke for tension patches method to prevent tearing the pad shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 12. Restraint system for static testing

Fig. 13. Tes loading system

The applied actuators are 36 channels and the data sensors are 800 channels. The full scale ground setup is shown in Fig. 14. The tests have been conducted to limit and ultimate loads to verify the structures behaviors of no detrimental permanent deformation and no failure respectively. Finally, the test was processed up to the failure load. As shown in Fig. 15, the structures of Smart UAV can sustain up to the 165 % one of the critical load.

Fig. 14. Test Setup

Fig. 15. Test Results

The ground vibration test has been performed to obtain frequencies, mode shapes and structural

damping. The first flight prototype for vibration test is hung with bungee rope as shown in Fig. 16. Fig. 17 and Fig. 18 are the results of frequencies. The fundamental mode with 8.25 Hz is wing vibration coupled with stabilizer mode. The second one with 10.23 Hz occurs at vertical stabilizer. The test Data obtained will be used for comparison with FEM data used in determining the flutter speed.

Fig. 16. Ground vibration test setup
(a)

Fig. 17. Results of ground vibration test

Fig. 18. Mode Shapes

4. Concluding Remarks

The Structures of Smart UAV have been developed using composite materials except for fittings, and bulkheads, and supporting plates required electric bonding. The design loads are defined in the maneuverings of helicopter, airplane and transition modes for the tilt rotor type. The design is based on

3D modeling using CATIA system. Based on structural simplification, reduced part count, and easy handling, the structures are designed. The total parts are below 250 pieces. For the structural integrity and robustness of the composite airframe, the building block approach for testing and evaluation was processed. The design allowable test data obtained were used in stress analysis performed by NASTRAN. As the results of the full scale static test, the structures of Smart UAV can hold up to the 165 % one of the design loads. Based on the test results, the second flight airframe was manufactured for easy accessibility and maintainability and weight reduction.

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